

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННЫМ НАВЫКАМ

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TEACHING STUDENTS INTEGRATED SKILLS

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье: «Обучение интегрированным навыкам» рассматривается использование метода CLIL, что означает изучение материала по определенному предмету и в то же время изучение английского языка. Подчеркивается роль аутентичных видеоматериалов, которые рассматриваются как функциональные и коммуникативные средства обучения, удовлетворяющие потребности и интересы обучающихся. Метод предметно - языкового интегрированного обучения помогает обучающимся интегрировать свои знания и умения из различных предметов и применить интегрированные знания и навыки для решения проблем в реальной жизни. В данной статье даются примеры краткосрочных планов уроков по биологии и другим предметам естественно-математического цикла с применением метода CLIL.

ABSTRACT

The article: "Teaching integrated skills" considers CLIL method as both learning the material in a particular subject and learning English at the time.

Visual authentic materials are considered to be functional and have communicative integrity due to which they meet learners' needs. CLIL method helps to integrate their skills from different subjects such as Biology, information Technology and other sciences, consolidation of complex application of knowledge and skills for solving problems in real life. The samples of short-term lesson plans in Biology and IT are considered in this article. Video materials and project work of learners are said to be functional and have communicative integrity.

Ключевые слова: эффект пропеллирования; движение относительно центра масс; наноспутники стандарта CubeSat, момент пропеллирования; наноспутники с раскрывающимися солнечными панелями.

Keywords: integrated skills, CLIL method, functional, project, and communicative integrity short-term plans.

CLIL is one of the most contemporary methods of teaching integrated skills, communicative skills, and content knowledge which is both learning the material in a particular subject such as Biology or Physics, for example, and at the same time learning the English language. Great attention has been paid to the use of authentic materials in the lessons of Biology, Physics, math, and other subjects which are taught in English. Why are authentic materials considered to be the most effective means of teaching both foreign languages and a certain subject such as Physics or Biology? Authentic materials are functional and have communicative integrity due to which they meet learners' needs and activate their thinking activity.

In modern conditions, teachers need to take into account the following didactic principles such as:

Systematic involvement of students in autonomy activity of applying their acquired knowledge in different sciences and real situations

- Ability to use and integrate their knowledge using cross-curricular links as integral and complex

- Transition from reproductive activity to a productive one.

- Teaching students to solve complex problems, which is supposed to be able to transfer knowledge and skills from different subjects such as Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Economics, Maths, Geography and consolidation of complex application of knowledge and

skills for solving real problems in our life and labor for improving our quality of life.

- It is necessary to teach our learners to use laboratory equipment correctly and safely, to follow the rules of technical safety, and their ability to fix the results of surveys and measurements with the help of different things such as drawings, tables, graphs, photos, video records, schemes.

- In the lessons of Biology, Physics, Chemistry, and Geography, as well as in Information Technology and Maths, students learn to carry out practical and laboratory assignments, they learn to analyze and compare, generalize and synthesize, they evaluate and make forecasts, make calculations, explain quantity and quality characteristics of different phenomena and processes in nature and organisms. Students are taught to work on different projects, they learn to work in teams or groups while working on projects and each student has a good opportunity to develop his natural abilities and creativity, as well as responsibility for the task given to him and autonomy individual potential.

- Students develop practically - orientated thinking abilities, when in the lessons of Biology, Physics, Chemistry, Maths, Geography, and IT when teachers widely use Information- Communication Technologies. And teach learners to work with information in electronic form.

- Computer technologies in the lessons of Biology, Physics, and other natural sciences can be the following types:

1. Intensive use of multi-media technologies during the process of learning the course material
2. Intensive use of computers as tools for everyday work by teachers and students.
3. Carrying out the technologies of cross-curricular links
4. Project and research work of students
5. Searching and treatment of the information in terms of the target material using the Internet
6. Use of electronic tables for solving problems
7. Holding virtual practice and laboratory work.

Taking into account the specifications of studying natural sciences such as Biology, Physics, Geography, Chemistry it has become very important for learners to work on research projects that can be done in three directions:

1. theoretical research (group research, individual ones connected with theory research and work with the information and its selection and analysis)
2. Empirical research (practical and laboratory work)
3. Individual research projects

Teachers can choose the themes of practical work and laboratory work autonomously, taking into consideration the equipment and other technologies, and school facilities. Every student should be assessed for his or her practice or laboratory work.

In this article, I want to give some examples of a short-term lesson plan based on the CLIL method in Biology.

The theme of the lesson is: The theory of Evolution

Lesson aim: In this lesson, students learn about the theory of evolution established by Charles Darwin.

1 The lesson starts with a warm-up exercise. The teacher writes the words on the board: Darwinism, evolution, natural selection. Then teacher finds out what students know about evolution, Darwinism, and natural selection. The teacher explains that learners are going to read the text about the history of Darwinism. Then the teacher asks if they can remember any information related to the words.

2 At the second stage the teacher draws learners' attention to the photos on the interactive board or

On the projector and in pairs asks them to guess who Charles Darwin was.

Then the teachers offer the learners to read the text quickly and then answer the questions on the text.

When was the theory of evolution established?

Who was Charles Darwin and what was he famous for?

Before reading the text again, the teacher should remind students of the facts they learned in the Warmer, and go through the words in the Glossary box. Then the teacher asks them to find them in the text and pre-teach some of the more complex words if necessary.

3 Students read the text again in detail and fill in the missing information in the diagram.

A. Variation: individuals of species cannot be fully identical. For instance, siblings might be of different heights and have different eye colors.

B. Inheritance: traits of species are determined by inheritance and passed from generation to generation. In other words, offspring will inherit traits that are passed by genes.

C. Competition: more offspring are born than can survive given the scarcity of natural resources. To illustrate, members of the species compete for limited natural resources available, for instance, food

D. Natural selection: only the individuals who survived in the struggle for existence would be able to breed and pass on inherited traits to the offspring. More officially, the traits that helped parents to survive will be passed on to the next generations.

The next task is to choose the correct alternative: true or false statements.

Then students work in groups and answer the questions about the text and support their answers with examples and solid arguments from the text or real life.

Students can be offered to work in groups on the project:

1. Choose one of the outstanding scientists in evolutionary biology.

2. Find out more about the scholar you have chosen. And what was their contribution? Think about the historical, economic, and political context they lived and worked in. Select information that is insightful and tries to collect multimedia files if possible. Consult with your Biology textbooks and seek advice from your teacher if you need it.

3. Make a poster about the discovery of your chosen scientist. Describe the steps of completing this project; indicate the sources of information, and photographs if possible. Try to highlight the public's reaction to the works of your chosen scientist and critically analyze whether the discovery was controversial and why. Present your poster to the class, be open to feedback, and reflect on what you have learned and what you would do differently next time.

This project can be given to students as homework.

Such creative assignments develop the autonomy of students, their logical and creative thinking abilities,

Also, such kinds of work teach students to work in groups, develop their communicative and language skills, their ability to work creatively and individually and to be responsible and active participants in the research work.

The role of video is very big in the lesson because when students present their projects, learners can see the presentation and they have a good opportunity to memorize the information because visually helps them to understand the material better and deeper, and such materials make the lesson more interesting, memorable and understandable for every student.

V.I. Pisarenko says that the use of video materials in the lesson can be explained in the following way:

1. availability of video materials that can be recorded from different resources

2. a certain experience of how to use video materials

3. more active and creative activities of instructors { 30, p .77-81 }

Elukhina N.V., Komarova YU.E., Mikheeva I.V., Shabalin YU.V. have researched the use of video materials and the analysis has shown that video materials enhance the following things:

- a) forming students' steady associations of a certain context with expected speech behavior
- b) stimulation of learners' imagination and creative activity
- c) developing all types of learners' memory
- d) creating a friendly atmosphere
- e) Learners' motivation
- f) Effective learning outcomes

Video materials shouldn't be too difficult and they should correspond to learners' level, age, and interests and the content should be motivating and carefully selected according to students' needs and future careers.

As we have already said project work develops students' integrated skills, learners develop speaking, writing, and reading skills as well as knowledge in the particular subject on a definite theme in Biology.

Integrated skills can be developed also when we use Information Technology in our lessons, particularly when we provide information through PowerPoint presentations.

Here is an example of the use of ICT in the lesson.

This lesson aims to get students to learn how to design and deliver a PowerPoint Presentation.

In the first stage, we should have a warm-up discussion.

The following questions can be offered for discussion.

1. How often do you present information?
2. What programs do you use?
3. How often do you use PowerPoint presentations?

In the second stage, we can offer the students to look at the infographics and discuss them in pairs. Then we can elicit answers from the class and discuss why PowerPoint Presentation is the most popular program for designing presentations.

The next step is reading the text about making presentations using PowerPoint Presentation.

But before reading the text we should work on the new words from the text, that is pre-teach the topic vocabulary. We should write the words in the Glossary on the board and ask the students to find them in the text and explain the meanings of some more complex words if that is necessary.

Then students read the text and decide if the statements are true or false.

The next step is to focus learners' attention on the presentation tips and ask them to scan the text to find the correct answers.

Do's: develop a story and stay focused

Use visuals to present information

Make the presentation accessible

Back up the presentation

Practice

Don'ts: Don't use too much text on the slides

Don't use too many effects

Don't use a font size smaller than 28

Learners can be offered to make a project: Present information using the PowerPoint Presentation on the target theme, following the plan:

1. Choose a topic that interests you or that is part of your homework. Research prepares information on your theme and structures it. Follow this plan.

2. Create a PowerPoint presentation to inform your class about the topic. Add some infographics to your slides for data visualization.

3. Deliver the presentation in your class and welcome questions at the end. Evaluate each other using positive feedback.

This example of the lesson plan can be used full not only at the lessons of Biology but in other Lessons such as Physics, Chemistry, Maths,

Geography and other subjects. Such lessons give learners to understand the course material much better in Biology or Physics, it doesn't matter what subject it is, and learners improve their knowledge of English at the same time.

Another good example of combining education and technology is learning new material with the help of online courses in Biology or other subjects. We want to give an example of a short lesson plan on the theme: Online courses.

In the first stage we can offer the learners a few questions for discussion:

Have you learned online? Have you enjoyed online learning? Learners can discuss the questions in pairs or groups so we can find out what students think about online courses.

We can offer students reading an article about online courses and at first pre-teach new words which are difficult and then students read the text about the online course production. After reading the text they answer the questions in the text. Students learn information about the process of online course creation.

The third step is to complete the chart about the phases of creating the online course:

Pre- Production Phase 1: a project plan and course structure are produced.

Pre- Production Phase 2: online course lecture scripts are written

Production Phase 3: the online course is filmed

Post-Production Phase 4: video and audio are edited

Post-Production Phase 5: the online course is published on a platform

Post-Production Phase 6: a final product is presented and passed on to the next generations.

As for the home task students can be offered to work on the project: Work in a group and make a presentation about an online course.

Imagine that you are designing your online course in Biology. Decide what theme you would like to choose, and brainstorm the content, structure, teaching methods, and key learning outcomes.

Look at the course you have researched in Step 1 and use it to present your course.

In your group, prepare a presentation to launch your online course to the rest of the class.

In conclusion, we want to say that project work develops learners' ability to work creatively, to make

research and work collaboratively and solve problems, this project method contributes to learners' integration of knowledge and skills and combines a particular subject with Technology. Students have a good opportunity to use their knowledge in different subjects and link this knowledge to get a new skill or new knowledge. Students' knowledge of Technology, Biology, and English are integrated and orientate students to choose their future careers successfully and purposefully.

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